

Detailed Technical Documentation of the INPUT and OUTPUT stage system

Deliverable 5.1

Submission Date: 30 November 2020

Lead Partner: KOUR ENERGY

Contributor(s): UNIMORE

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

HORECA and ROW is full of raw materials to feed insects like Black Soldier Fly (BSF) *Hermetia illucens* (Diptera, Stratiomyidae), who can efficiently convert kitchen, restaurant and caterer scraps or organic materials into a biomass rich in proteins, lipids and chitin. SCALIBUR is following a sustainable and resilient approach to shifting the production of protein onto a more sustainable path and also to valorise the chitin, as an important natural polymer.

In order to obtain these high value products from Black Soldier Fly (BSF) is needed to address the mass rearing insects on organic waste by optimizing the prototype pilot plant of UNIMORE and integrating the INPUT stage for substrate preparation and the OUTPUT stage for insect treatment and stabilization.

This report summarises the technical activities carried out with regards to the "INPUT" and "OUTPUT" stages of the pilot plant subject of SCALIBUR WP5.

For more information, contact:

Project Coordinator: César Aliaga, caliaga@itene.com

Project Communications: James Ling, j.ling@greenovate-europe.eu

Deliverable contact: Giacomo Benassi, giacomobenassi@kourenergy.com